

Content Security Policy – How hard can it be?

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Abstract: The Content Security Policy (CSP) is an important method for protection of web applications. Correct implementation is highly challenging. Many developers and administrators therefore omit it entirely. However, smart implementation is possible – and advisable.

Keywords: Area41, Block, Browser, Checkpoint, Firefox, Google, HTML, HTTP, Internet Explorer, Javascript

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2016 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160818> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

The *Content Security Policy* [1] (CSP) has been a separate checkpoint for our *Web Application Penetration Tests* [2] since September 2015. One of the first projects so tested is emblematic of the acceptance and implementation of CSP in general. In that project, multiple cross-site scripting (XSS) vulnerabilities were found. Along with strict input validation, we also recommended introduction of a CSP header as an additional measure. The developers implemented this and defined a policy. But the `script-src` directive continued to permit execution of *inline JavaScript*. This effectively meant installation of a policy that offered no real protection against XSS attacks. In the end, the CSP header was taken out again. No additional resources were invested in a stricter policy definition or an amendment to the web application.

Introduction of an effective Content Security Policy is a demanding task, one that should be carried out in accordance with web development. This article describes how CSP came about and how it is used in practice.

3. Emergence and development

The first draft of the *Content Security Policy Level 1* [3] was published by the *W3C Consortium* [4] on 15 November 2012. Browser vendors initially implemented it as an experimental function with the header `X-Content-Security-Policy` or `X-WebKit-CSP`.

The goal of CSP is to provide both web developers and web server administrators with a tool for mitigation of injection vulnerabilities. When this kind of policy is defined, the web

browser is informed which web application resources will be loaded and processed, such as images, style sheets (CSS) or scripts. Here, CSP should be considered a component of a *defense-in-depth strategy* rather than a replacement for input validation or coding of output.

The `X-Content-Security-Policy` header is supported by Mozilla Firefox (since Version 4) and Microsoft Internet Explorer 10, but is already considered obsolete and should no longer be used. The `Content-Security-Policy` header stands for CSP Level 1 and all further levels. It has been supported since browser versions Google Chrome 25, Mozilla Firefox 23, Safari 7 and Internet Explorer Edge.

Through *directives*, the policy can be tailored to the intended use of the web application. A directive is an instruction to a web browser how to handle several resource types. The `default-src` directive is considered the standard for all other directives where they are not specified. Directives exist for management of JavaScript, images, objects and style sheets (CSS). Each directive is defined by a *source expression*. Valid values include `none`, `self`, `data`: and one or more *hosts/domains*. The *Content Security Policy Reference* [5] offers a good overview.

In the case of the directive for JavaScript named `script-src`, it became apparent that the existing *source expressions* were insufficient for real-life scenarios and thus inhibited implementation of CSP. With *Level 2* [6], published on 21 July 2015, the attribute `nonce` was introduced to ensure additional flexibility. The following section discusses its use – and shortcomings.

The `frame-ancestors` directive was also introduced with the aim of replacing the HTTP header `X-Frame-Options`. Here, the expression `none` equates to the value `DENY` in the HTTP header. Veit Hailperin already explained this header in his article *Inglorious Headers* [7]. For now we recommend a dual use strategy, set the policy and the header for it self because not all browsers support this CSP level.

The `nonce` attribute has not caught on in practice. It was the inclusion of JavaScript libraries from third-party sites that proved particularly problematic. The introduction of the source expression `strict-dynamic` in the *Working Draft* [8] for the CSP Level 3 dated 21 June 2016 attempts to solve this. As a further change, the directive `report-uri` was renamed `report-to`.

4. Use in conjunction with JavaScript

Where CSP has not previously been used, we recommend starting with the following directive:

```
default-src "none"; script-src "self";
connect-src "self"; img-src "self"; style-src
"self";
```

This will allow the use of images, styles (CSS) and JavaScript from your own domain. When using JavaScript, however, this also means that only integrated script files are executed. Any in-line instructions in script tags are not permitted. For web applications developed in this way, this leads to the problem that the `script` element is processed directly in the HTML code.

To avoid recoding the entire website, the directive is usually expanded to include the expression `unsafe-inline`. This means that the web application continues to function as usual, but is once again vulnerable to reflected or stored XSS attacks. This removes the benefit, or protective effect, of the policy.

In many web applications, the use of JavaScript is not restricted to the owner's domain. External libraries are also integrated into the context of the owner's page. This means that a whitelist of such domains has to be maintained in the `script-src` directive. Maintenance is no easy matter and in a worst-case scenario can even lead to a CSP bypass. This is vividly illustrated in solutions for the mini-challenge by *Cure53* [9] entitled "H5SC Minichallenge 3: Sh*t, its CSP!" [10].

With the introduction of the attribute `nonce` in CSP Level 2, there is now the option of use of embedded script elements. The principle behind `nonce` is that a random `nonce` value is recorded in the `script-src` directive. Ideally, this occurs through the web application itself. Every script element that sets this value in the `nonce` attribute is then authorized. This means that legitimate script elements are executed, but XSS attacks are stopped.

The use of libraries, including JavaScript CDNs like *jQuery*, *React.js* and *AngularJS*, in conjunction with `nonce` leads to a new problem as described below. The `nonce` attribute is defined as:

```
Content-Security-Policy: script-src "nonce-
i7bGtfs"
```

A library is then integrated into the website and correctly provided with the matching value in the `nonce` attribute:

```
<script
src="https://cdn.example.com/script.js"
nonce="i7bGtfs"></script>
```

Because the correct value for `nonce` is set, the integration of the library is permitted. But if further libraries are reloaded

as dependencies in the library itself or a script element is used, this leads to an error since the value for `nonce` is not set there. The second case relates to *parser-inserted* [11] script elements. A simple example of a *parser-inserted* element looks like this:

```
var scriptPath = "https://othercdn.not-
example.net/dependency.js"
document.write("<script src=" + scriptPath +
"></script>");
```

With the expression `strict-dynamic`, CSP Level 3 offers a solution for this problem and simplifies the use of external libraries. Using `strict-dynamic` in conjunction with `nonce` results in two changes, or effects:

1. The whitelists defined in the directives `default-src` or `script-src`, as well as the use of `unsafe-inline`, are rejected.
2. Reloading of dependencies in integrated libraries and script elements that are not *parser-inserted* are now permitted.

For practical purposes, this offers two benefits. The first effect permits a backwards-compatible rollout of `strict-dynamic`. The policy

```
Content-Security-Policy: "unsafe-inline"
https: "nonce-abcdefg" "strict-dynamic"
```

becomes `unsafe-inline https:` in browsers that support CSP Level 1. The `https: "nonce-abcdefg" "strict-dynamic"` applies in browsers that have implemented CSP Level 3. The second effect entrusts the integrated script with the integration of its own dependencies without the need to list them specifically in the whitelist.

One worthwhile presentation on CSP bypasses and the introduction of `strict-dynamic` is the talk by *Lukas Weichselbaum* [12] and *Michele Spagnuolo* [13], both information security engineers at Google, entitled *Breaking Bad CSP!* [14] at this year's *Area41 2016* [15]. The *slides* [16] from the talk are also available.

5. Reporting

The `Content-Security-Policy` header instructs the web browser to enforce the defined directives. This can, and experience shows that it does, lead to problems with the introduction of CSP or in the development phase of web applications. Therefore, a second CSP header called `Content-Security-Policy-Report-Only` reports infringements of the directive without blocking them. The web browser sends a report to the URL defined in the directive `report-uri` or, in future, `report-to`.

The report contains the following elements:

- `document-uri` – the page where the infringement occurred
- `referrer` – the referrer of the page
- `blocked-uri` – the base address of the blocked URI
- `violated_directive` – the specific directive that was infringed
- `original-policy` – the complete CSP

These reports can be evaluated in respect to overly strict directives, infringements of the directive caused by programming errors or flaws in the web application, as well as potential XSS attacks. The IT security researcher *Scott Helme* [17] offers a free service for collating and evaluating CSP reports at the website *report-uri.io* [18]. This website is suitable for a first attempt with CSP without the need to build a reporting infrastructure, or with publicly accessible websites that do not contain sensitive data. For sensitive websites, the report service should be operated by a system under your own control.

6. How hard can it be?

With `strict-dynamic`, Content Security Policy Level 3 provides a function that offers sufficient flexibility for productive use. The reporting function also offers a reasonable estimation of the consequences of implementation of CSP. This function means that you can test, step by step, how individual directives are configured, so that they offer the greatest level of restriction without hindering the functionality of the website. Web development itself ideally should conform to a policy and essentially refrain from use of *inline* functions for CSS or JavaScript. Since 2012, continuous work has been carried out on CSP to improve its functionality and simplify its implementation. CSP should no longer be seen as a bogeyman that endangers website operations, but rather as

another layer in a secure web application. We would certainly prefer to be able to analyze more CSP headers in the future, instead of simply entering *the CSP header is not set* in the checklist.

7. External Links

- [1] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20091009>
- [2] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?offense>
- [3] <https://www.w3.org/TR/2012/CR-CSP-20121115/>
- [4] <https://www.w3.org/>
- [5] <https://content-security-policy.comwebsite>
- [6] <https://www.w3.org/TR/CSP/>
- [7] <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20160121>
- [8] <https://www.w3.org/TR/CSP3/>
- [9] <https://cure53.de/>
- [10] <http://bit.ly/2aXz5SO>
- [11] <https://www.w3.org/TR/html5/scripting-1.html#parser-inserted>
- [12] <https://twitter.com/we1x>
- [13] <https://twitter.com/mikispag>
- [14] <https://www.youtube-nocookie.com/watch?v=q3jTkZlpcXw>
- [15] <https://area41.io/>
- [16] <http://www.slideshare.net/LukasWeichselbaum/breaking-bad-csp>
- [17] <https://scotthelme.co.uk/>
- [18] <https://report-uri.io/>